

(1) Overview

A lightweight, automated neural network-based stage-specific malaria detection software using dimension reduction

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Abstract

Artificial intelligence (AI) can outperform human in various applications, including diagnostics. Due to climate change and the COVID-19 pandemic, the number of malaria infections is rising. Reversing this trend and eliminating malaria worldwide requires improvements in malaria diagnosis, in which AI has recently been demonstrated to have a great potential.

Here we describe an AI-based approach that boosts the performance of light, atomic force and fluorescence microscopy-based malaria diagnosis. As the main challenge, the stage-specific recognition of infected red blood cells (RBCs) usually requires large sets of microscopy images for training a neural network, which is difficult to obtain. Our tool the Malaria Stage Classifier provides a fast, high-accuracy recognition which works even with limited training sets due to a smart reduction of data dimension. Individual RBCs are extracted from an image, reduced to characteristic one-dimensional cross-sections, and classified. The method is applicable to images recorded by various microscopy techniques. It is housed within a GitHub repository at https://github.com/KatharinaPreissinger/Malaria_stage_classifier.

Keywords

Malaria, red blood cells, malaria diagnosis, artificial intelligence, neural network, cell detection, software

Introduction

Background

More ancient than human, malaria has caused millions of deaths until today [1]. While it has been known for more than 4 thousand years [2], the most common technique used worldwide is still light microscopy of Giemsa-stained blood smears, which is time-consuming and heavily relies on human performance. To overcome these issues, computer-aided recognition of malaria-infected red blood cells (RBCs) has recently gained high attention.

As the number of cases is increasing due to the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic and climate change, the need for rapid and easily accessible recognition of the disease is rising. The infection is caused by five types of the *Plasmodium* genus, upon which *Plasmodium falciparum* causes the most deaths. Injected into the human body by a mosquito bite, the malaria parasites migrate to the liver cells, where they begin a phase of asexual reproduction, which is followed by the release of many thousands of merozoites. During their 48 h cycle in the blood stream, the parasites invade healthy RBCs and mature through three main stages—the ring, the trophozoite, and the schizont stage—, while altering the morphological and optical properties of the host RBCs [3, 4].

These well-explored transformations of the infected RBCs provide the basis for neural network (NN) based stage-specific recognition of malaria-infected RBCs in blood smears [5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10]. While clearly demonstrating the potential of NNs in malaria diagnosis, these pioneering approaches still face problems, e.g., in terms of sensitivity to different malaria species and stages. The following studies illustrate the state-of-the-art in this field.

Based on recent advances in high-resolution imaging techniques applied for the analysis of malaria-infected RBCs, especially topographic imaging [3, 11, 12] and infrared nano-imaging [13], recent studies on unstained RBCs [4] have demonstrated the applicability of NNs to analyse not only light microscopy images but also images recorded with other microscopy techniques. These works imply that, when combined with NN-based analysis, malaria diagnosis may be extended to other imaging methods.

One of the main reasons for the use of NNs is the time saving through automatising the process and the elimination of human error, when working with big amounts of data [14]. The majority of the algorithms developed for the analysis of malaria-infected RBCs up to now are limited to Giemsa-stained images and rely on a two-stage recognition, sorting healthy RBCs from infected ones, followed by a stage-specific categorisation of the infected cells [15, 16, 17, 18]. These algorithms have reached performances of $\sim 80\text{-}98\%$ with little or no pre-processing of microscopy images [19, 20, 21, 22]. By adding characteristic attributes of the RBCs, including the colour scheme [16], the morphology of the RBCs [17] and their other statistical features [18] to the analysis, similar results have been achieved.

When working with two-dimensional data images, the number of parameters, that has to be fitted by the NN for the classification of RBCs, is extremely high, which strongly influences the performance of the network. This issue can be solved by reducing the dimension of the input data and may even improve the classification [23].

To handle the loss of data that comes with the reduction of the dimension, features can be selected, which capture the characteristic properties of the RBCs [17, 24, 18]. The complicated handling of malaria culturing and sample preparation introduces some limitations to the application of NNs. They typically result in a small training set of a few thousands of images and an uneven distribution of RBC categories. The latter leads to overfitting [25], significantly influencing the performance of the network. One way out of this dilemma is the use of data augmentation, which increases the number of images and equalises the distribution of healthy and infected RBCs [19, 20], thus improves the performance of the classification [21, 22].

The Malaria Stage Classifier software was developed for the classification of RBCs into four categories: healthy, infected by ring-, trophozoite-, and schizont-stage malaria parasites, based on two characteristic cuts through the RBCs. The program is freely accessible and can handle text data and images from various microscopy techniques as input. The user interface is divided into tabs, making it easy to follow the step-wise analysis of the data (the individual cell detection followed by the classification of the single RBCs into four categories) and allows manual corrections of the predictions, which are saved in a table. It further provides the opportunity to expand the pre-trained neural network with new data. Due to its simple concept, the algorithm can easily be extended beyond the evaluation and classification of parasites and cells to include the classification of further types of objects.

Implementation and architecture

The input images were taken from our study on the morphological and optical properties of malaria-infected RBCs [3, 8, 26], which were recorded by three fundamentally different imaging techniques: Giemsa-stained light microscopy, AFM, and fluorescence microscopy. The data set contains 173 AFM images, 1232 fluorescence microscopy images and 792 Giemsa-stained light microscopy images, where we used 747 from [26] and recorded 45. All images were classified by human experts into the four stages: healthy, infected by ring-, trophozoite-, and schizont. Prior to training the NN, the stage distribution of the images was equalised by data augmentation. The final database contains approx. 70 thousand single cell images of all four categories for each microscopy technique.

As the success of the cell detection depends on the contrast of the imaging method, the AFM images are segmented prior to cell detection, which is not necessary for the light and fluorescence microscopy images, as they clearly stand out against the background. To identify the cells, the Hough gradient method is applied to the image. Following the cell detection, the characteristic features of the RBCs are extracted from the image and given to a pre-trained NN for classification. The prediction for each cell is returned in form of an image, where all cells are assigned to one of the four categories. In case of false classifications, the algorithm offers the option to change the assigned category. The detected cells can be added to the training set and the network training can be further refined with the new images. Our fully automatised analysis of malaria-infected RBCs in microscopy images delivers information about the number of cells and their state of infection. With this simple implementation, we provide fast and reliable classification for the diagnosis of malaria in microscopy images.

Segmenting and image processing

To increase the contrast of the image, we calculated the thresholding value for the AFM data by Otsu’s method [27]. Here, the user can change the preset value, if necessary. The resulting binary mask is then handled by the Hough gradient method [28, 29] to detect individual RBCs in the image. In case of light and fluorescence microscopy, the images can be modified prior to individual-cell detection by increasing brightness, contrast, colour, and sharpness [30](PIL image enhance). The thresholding is not applied to either method. Optionally, the cell recognition can be controlled by five parameters, which describe the minimum distance between the centres of two objects, the measure of how strong the edges of the circles need to be, the number of edges the algorithm has to find to declare the object a circle, the minimum and maximum radius. To facilitate the use of the program, the parameters are predefined for all implemented imaging methods.

Extraction of characteristic features

The second step in our analysis was selecting characteristic cross-sections of single-RBC images. By measuring the asymmetry of the RBCs, we were able to capture the absence or presence of the parasite in two cross-sections, where one goes through the geometric centre r_{geo} and the centre of "mass" r_{mass} and the other is perpendicular to the first and only crosses r_{geo} . Both are calculated by using the circle fit of the contour and the conventional definitions of the two centers:

$$r_{\text{geo}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i,j} r_{ij} \quad (1)$$

$$r_{\text{mass}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i,j} h(r_{ij})r_{ij}, \quad (2)$$

where $r_{(i,j)}$ denotes the position of the pixel with the x and y coordinates i and j , respectively, and the summation goes over all N pixels within the interior of the RBC. In the second sum, $h(r_{ij})$ denotes the height (AFM) or intensity (light and fluorescence microscopy) of a pixel at $r_{i,j}$.

This process is run in the background and not visible to the user. The calculated features are provided as input to the NN for the classification of the RBCs.

Neural network

Three simple convolutional neural networks with four convolutional, four max pooling, and two dense layers are provided for the stage-specific classification of the RBCs in the input image. They were pre-trained on approx. 70000 single cell cross-sections, including all four categories of the malaria parasite. The training, test and validation data are provided within the software package for each of the microscopy techniques.

Architecture

The algorithm was implemented in Python 3.7 with *numpy* [31] and *pandas* [32] for the data analysis. For the cell detection, we used *OpenCV* [33] together with *skimage* [34] and *matplotlib 3.5.2* [35] for the data visualisation. To integrate the pre-trained NN, *tensorflow* [36] with *keras* was included in the algorithm. The interface was built with *tkinter* [37]. To handle the errors and the output files, the libraries *os*, *sys*, *csv*, and *traceback* were imported. The library *webbrowser* opens system folders and external links.

The program is built with five tabs, where each performs one step of the stage-specific classification of RBCs. Starting with the general settings, the algorithm only allows text or image files as input. Depending on the file type, the number of header lines in a text file can be set. As the program is designed for multiple imaging methods, the respective technique determines the possible actions on the input file. The settings are completed by selecting an output path and the output file type (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: **Setting of initial parameters:** input image, its format, imaging method, memory location of the results

In the second tab, the input image is displayed to show the location and stage of the cells (Fig. 2).

If the image was recorded by AFM, the next step requires thresholding to enhance the contrast. While the value can be adapted manually, the algorithm suggests a pre-calculated number. In case of the light microscopy techniques, this step is skipped (Fig. 3).

Figure 2: **Show image**: input file is shown as image

The next tab triggers the cell detection, which is based on the Hough gradient method for the recognition of circular objects. Depending on the size, contrast, and brightness of the image, the algorithm offers the option to control the detection by manually changing the calculation parameters and allows contrast enhancement. During this step, the dimension of the input data is reduced to two cross-sections, which capture the strongest features associated with the presence or absence and the stage of the malaria parasites (Fig. 4).

In the final part of the program, the pre-trained CNNs are loaded and used for the stage-specific prediction of the detected RBCs. This triggers the option to change the false predictions accordingly. The algorithm further provides the possibility to add new data and to retrain the NN. The last step returns the statistics of the analysed RBCs in form of a text file or table (Fig. 5).

Every tab is connected to user actions and disabled until all required parameters have been set or calculated. The algorithm follows the concept of object-oriented programming (OOP), containing two classes for the user interface, one class for the AFM and light microscopy images with two subclasses respectively, and one class for the geometric properties of the RBCs, including the cell centres and characteristic cuts. The cell detection and the calculation of the characteristic features are implemented in separate files. Detailed descriptions of the classes and methods can be found in the documentation (<https://malaria-stage-classifier.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>).

Figure 3: **Threshold image**: option to enhance the image contrast by thresholding (disabled for light and fluorescence microscopy)

Figure 4: **Detect cells:** RBCs are detected by the Hough gradient method. To fine-tune, the image can be enhanced and the parameters for the detection set manually.

Figure 5: **Cell classification:** RBC stages are predicted and can be altered manually. Optionally, the neural network can be retrained with new data. The result of the evaluation is saved with “Save predictions”.

Quality control

The program was extensively tested manually on 45 microscopy images, 15 text files and 30 tif files. Prior to the development of the interface-based algorithm, the accuracy of the cell detection, the extraction of characteristic parameters, and the performance of the neural network, were evaluated.

Cell detection

To validate the cell detection program, we tested 200 images for each of the three different imaging techniques (light microscopy, fluorescence microscopy, AFM) used in our study. In the first step, we had to select the imaging method. In case of AFM, the image was thresholded by Otsu's method. The position of the cell geometrical center and the cell radius were calculated with the Hough gradient method implemented in the program. The detected cells were then compared with the actual number of cells in the image. Our analysis showed that we were able to detect 95% of the cells with our method.

As the Hough gradient method is used to find circular objects in an image, it fails for cells strongly deviating from their normal round shape. While the algorithm might still detect such a cell, the circle will be much larger than the original object. Another problem are overlapping cells, which distort the circular shape of the cells. In most of these cases, the algorithm is able to tell them apart. While there is still room for optimisation of the detection process, we opted for an easy and fast method, which shows a high detection rate.

Characteristic cuts of single-RBC images

To test the calculation of the centres, at the first stage we created artificial images of white circles without hole and with a black hole, centred or off-centred, located randomly inside the circle, proving that our algorithm works correctly. Then, we visually inspected, if the cut goes through the parasite, analysing approx. 5000 images of RBCs containing ring- and trophozoite-stage parasites, including all three imaging techniques. While the success rate was between 50-60% in case of the light microscopy and AFM ring-stage parasites, it went up to 88% for the fluorescence images. With more than 85% for the trophozoite-stage parasite for light microscopy and AFM and 95% for fluorescence microscopy, the hit rate is much higher. As the schizont-stage parasites fill up most of the host cell, they were not analysed because they are necessarily cut by the asymmetric cross-section.

Our method is sensitive to changes in intensity, therefore its success strongly depends on the contrast. Especially in case of misaligned contours or overlapping cells in images with low contrast, the background plays a large role, which is shown by the success rate reached on the single-RBC images of ring-stage parasites.

Neural network

To predict the stages of the RBCs, our convolutional neural network was trained on approx. 60000 and tested on approx. 8000 sets of characteristic cross-sections,

for each imaging method respectively. Fig. 6 shows a confusion matrix for all three techniques. The precision is defined as the ratio of correctly classified results and all results classified as the respective row, while the recall represents the ratio of correctly classified results and all results belonging to the respective column. The overall performance of the NN is then defined as the ratio of correctly classified cells, independent of the category, and all classified cells. With an overall performance of more than 98% on the test sets, our method proves its applicability for RBC analysis on microscopy images.

		Light microscopy AFM Fluorescence microscopy					
		Healthy	Ring	Trophozoite	Schizont		
Predicted stages	Healthy	1582 1845 2704 23.3% 24.9% 22.9%	7 0 19 0.1% 0.0% 0.2%	0 0 0 0.0% 0.0% 0.0%	0 7 4 0.0% 0.1% 0.0%	99.6% 99.6% 99.2%	
	Ring	43 17 144 0.6% 0.2% 1.2%	1689 1847 2924 24.9% 24.9% 24.8%	0 0 2 0.0% 0.0% 0.0%	0 0 10 0.0% 0.0% 0.1%	97.5% 99.1% 94.9%	
	Trophozoite	24 12 16 0.4% 0.2% 0.1%	0 0 0 0.0% 0.0% 0.0%	1758 1849 3034 25.9% 24.9% 25.7%	0 0 0 0.0% 0.0% 0.0%	98.7% 99.4% 99.5%	
	Schizont	14 19 44 0.2% 0.3% 0.9%	0 0 0 0.0% 0.0% 0.0%	3 0 0 0.0% 0.0% 0.0%	1661 1820 2906 24.5% 24.5% 24.6%	99.0% 99.0% 98.5%	
		95.1% 97.5% 93.0%	95.1% 97.5% 93.0%	99.8% 100% 99.9%	100% 99.6% 99.5%	98.7% 99.3% 98.0%	
		Recall				Precision	

Figure 6: **Performance of the NN on characteristic cross-sections.** The classification results on the test set, as obtained on 2D cross-sections of light microscopy (black), AFM (blue) and fluorescence microscopy (red) images, are respectively summarised in the confusion matrix. The labels of the rows are the categories predicted by the NN-based classifier, while the labels of the columns indicate the classification by human experts. The diagonal elements show the correctly predicted cells, while the off-diagonal elements correspond to false classifications. The last column shows the precision for each category, while the recall is shown in the bottom row. Each field displays the number of counts and the corresponding percentage with respect to the total number of cells in the test set. The overall classification performance is displayed in the grey field in the bottom right corner.

(2) Availability

Operating system

The code will run under Windows (Windows 7 or higher) and Ubuntu 20.4 and was tested on Windows 10 and Ubuntu 20.4.

Programming language

Python 3.7. (minimum Python 3.7)

Additional system requirements

Up to 250 MB of free disk space.

Dependencies

matplotlib 3.5.2

numpy 1.19.2

opencv 4.1.1

pandas 1.2.4

skimage 0.18.1

sklearn 0.24.1

tensorflow 2.5.0

tkinter 8.6

List of contributors

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Software location:

Archive

Dataset for NN

Name: Malaria Stage Classifier dataset

Persistent identifier: <https://zenodo.org/record/6866337>

Publisher: Katharina Preißinger

Version published: 1.0

Date published: September 15, 2022

Software

Name: Malaria Stage Classifier

Persistent identifier: <https://zenodo.org/record/6881880>

Publisher: Katharina Preißinger

Version published: 1.0

Date published: September 15, 2022

Code repository

Name: Malaria_stage_classifier

Persistent identifier

For software: https://github.com/KatharinaPreissinger/Malaria_stage_classifier

Licence: GNU General Public Licence version 3.0

Date published: September 15, 2022

Language

English

(3) Reuse potential

Here, we introduce a simple cell detection algorithm to classify malaria-infected RBCs in microscopy images into four categories: healthy, ring-, trophozoite-, and schizont-stage parasites. Our approach is not limited to a certain microscopy technique but demonstrated to be universally applicable for fundamentally different imaging techniques, which was demonstrated via the high classification accuracy

on images recorded with Giemsa-stained light microscopy, AFM, and fluorescence microscopy. The reduction of dimension by selecting characteristic features of the RBCs significantly boosts the speed and classification accuracy of the network. This simple concept can easily be applied for the classification of general objects.

Given the rising number of techniques, successfully applied for the imaging of RBCs, the algorithm can be augmented for any method with high contrast, formatted as text or image file. Researchers are encouraged to implement new methods themselves, as the documentation is easily understandable and can be found at <https://stage-specific-classification-of-rbc.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html#>. In case of low contrast microscopy images, the option of contrast improvement can be implemented, including thresholding for text files and the enhancement of brightness and contrast for image files.

Moreover, we provide the opportunity to increase the data set, which is used to train the NN, to improve the classification accuracy of the algorithm. After loading the NN and visually verifying the accuracy of the classifications, the researchers have the possibility to add the characteristic single-RBC cross-sections to the original images and to retrain the NN with the new data set. The dataset for the new training is deposited at <https://zenodo.org/record/6866337>.

Contact and support

The researchers have access to the full code with documentation. In case of problems, users are encouraged to report errors, ask questions, and provide suggestions for improvement via email to the corresponding author.

Acknowledgements

We thank Richard Izrael and Petra Molnár for their contribution to the classification of RBCs.

Funding statement

This research was supported by the National Research, Development and Innovation Office of Hungary (K119493, VEKOP-2.3.2-16-2017-00013, NKP-2018-1.2.1-NKP-2018-00005), the BME-Biotechnology FIKP grant of EMMI (BME FIKP-BIO), the BME-Nanotechnology and Materials Science FIKP grant of EMMI (BME FIKP-NAT), the National Heart Programme (NVKP-16-1-2016-0017), K124966 and K135360, National Bionics Programme ED_17-1-2017-0009 and SE FIKP-Therapy Grant.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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